

Composite Evaluation Using Ultrasonic Techniques

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ABSTRACT

Non-destructive testing of carbon fibre reinforced composites by ultrasonic techniques has received more attention to predict the performance of these composites. Various techniques are being used for finding the longitudinal stiffness and shear properties of these composites.

Present work deals with evaluation of carbon fibre-Kevlar fibre hybrid composites. Flat composites are fabricated with carbon fibres, Kevlar fibres and hybrid reinforcement in epoxy resins. Ultrasonic longitudinal wave velocity of these composites is measured parallel as well as perpendicular to the fibre direction at non-dispersive frequency of 10 MHz, using one probe pulse-echo method. The shift in velocity is attributed to the fibre matrix interactions and fibre interaction at differential interface boundaries.

Through transmission attenuation technique is used to predict the irregularities and voids produced during processing and introduced deliberately in the composites.

Ultrasonic stiffness of the composites is determined by using the above technique and compared with the measured young's modulus. It is found that the ultrasonic stiffness agrees well with the actual young's modulus of these composites.

